
Migration and Asylum Seekers Governance in the EU: The Case of Berlin Municipality

Mykhaylo Kunychka

University of Economics in Bratislava

Leonid Raneta

University of Economics in Bratislava

Abstract

The number of refugees seeking asylum protection in Europe has grown considerably in the last five years. In 2015 more than 1 million refugees and migrants crossed the borders of Germany, the biggest refugee destination in the European Union, in order to flee conflict and persecution. This paper will assess how refugees and asylum seekers are treated in the municipality of Berlin. The migration governance conducted by the local State office for refugee affairs will be examined as well. At a time of migration crisis that heavily passed across Europe, it is critically important to understand the practices and approaches for asylum seekers integration on the example of Berlin - refugees high concentrated area and one of the most effective municipalities for refugee adjustment activities. Housing services offered by local units for refugees and asylum seekers will be studied. According to German authorities the housing is a key issue in the long process of migrant integration as it provides a balance in in the private space of targeted group. ¹

Keywords: migration crisis, asylum seekers, migration governance, housing, Berlin

Introduction

The geopolitical tensions and humanitarian crisis in the neighboring regions of the European union have reached a great extent at the beginning of the 21st century, therefore spurred new problems for the whole international community. Today, one of the biggest challenges is the problem of migration that is most relevant to Europe due to social, security or environmental reasons (Tomety et al, 2018). The modern European migration crisis arose at the beginning of 2015 due to the multiple increase in the flow of refugees from the Middle East and North Africa. Modern migration has become a dynamic and complex process, which entails certain socio-economic and political consequences for various states. Migration directly affects the ethnic and cultural balance of countries and their economic and fiscal environment (d'Albis, Boubtane, & Coulibaly, 2018). In Germany, for instance, neofascists have attacked the police protecting refugees shelter near Dresden or vast protests have been conducted during the visit of Angela Merkel showing her support to migrants (Kunzig 2016). Moreover, at the present stage, migration is becoming a source of threat to security both for particular countries and for individuals and society.

Germany as one of the EU countries with open policy for migrants had received about 1.8 million refugees for the last 5 years. Only in 2015, this country opened its doors to more than 890 thousand refugees during the peak of the migration crisis in the region (Streitwieser et al, 2017). Berlin as a federal state and the city with its 12 districts has received around 5% share of nationwide numbers or about 95,000 persons (LAF 2020) and became the main absorber of the war refugees among the European cities (Soederberg 2018). The growing tendency of refugees and asylum seekers influx has led to a big challenge for local authorities to process, accommodate, and integrate newcomers into the social-economic and cultural life of the city. All the challenges emerged in the different fields of work with migrants in need, including education and participation in cultural life, accommodation, health, social services, or security issues.

This paper will assess how refugees and asylum seekers are treated in the municipality of Berlin in terms of housing. The migration governance conducted by the local State office for efugee affairs will be examined as well. At a time of migration

¹ This paper was generated within MAGYC project that has recieved funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 822806.

crisis that heavily passed across Europe, it is critically important to understand the practices and approaches for asylum seekers integration. Services offered for refugees by local authorities like housing and its impact on integration will be studied.

Historical background and contemporary issues

Berlin is known for its open migrant policy and the first city in the country to adopt a sort of integration policy. City of Berlin, as it has two administrative statuses (city and federal state), is best known for its multicultural heritage and a vast number of residents with foreign origin. About 1 million of 3,5 million inhabitants or 30% have at least a half foreign origin (one of the parents is a migrant) that can be associated with a long history of immigration into the city during the last 70 years, not mentioned the influx of French Huguenots during the 17-18 century (OECD, 2016). The migration during the post Second World war period driven by expanding industrialization and recruitment process of foreign low-skilled workers had left a big footprint on the ethnicity and cultural heterogeneity of the city as well.

According to the State office for refugee affairs in Berlin, from 2015 the city has received about 94 300 refugees from all over the world, including Syria, Iraq, Afghanistan, Turkey, Iran, Nigeria, Georgia, Somali, Russia, and Moldova (LAF, 2020). It is important to mention that Berlin does not receive the biggest share of all migrant coming to the country and has a portion of just 5% in comparison to another regional states like Nordrhein-Westfalen, Bayern or Baden-Wurttemberg. At the end of January 2020 there were around 21 000 refugees accommodated in three different types of reception centers that are distributed in the 12 districts of the city. The biggest share is situated in the north-east districts of the city such as Lichtenberg (16,3%), Marzahn-Hellersdorf (13,8%), and Pankow (13%), where the large accommodation facilities are situated. Southern districts like Tempelhof-Schöneberg and Steglitz-Zehlendorf have a share of 11% and 9%, respectively. Central districts like Mitte and Friedrichshain-Kreuzberg are the less refugee accommodated locations. The distribution of accommodated refugees is shown on the map below.

Map 1 Distribution of asylum seekers in Berlin districts by 31.01.2020, numbers of refugees and % of total

Source: processed by authors on the basis of LAF, 2020

After the peak of the migration crisis, Berlin like most of the receiving cities in Germany has focused on the homelessness of the refugees while not affecting the local dwellers. The municipality of Berlin has developed active policy measures to accommodate rising numbers of arriving migrants and created a State Office for Refugee Affairs in order to mitigate the problems with integration including housing, education, and social services. The creation of such a centralized municipal body has helped in the reduction of bureaucracy during the management and governance of immigration and enabled quick

policy decision and their implementation. The city has managed to distribute and house a big influx of newcomers since 2015 due to a rich history of immigration, governance mechanisms of integration and distribution as well as engagement of civil society, non-governmental organizations and residents.

Initial stages of housing and integration

Economic recovery and relatively affordable housing fees have led to a huge wave of migration to the city of Berlin and made a big pressure on the accommodation constraints in the past. After the fall of the Berlin Wall, the number of inhabitants has increased substantially, therefore created a challenge in offering housing to rising numbers of migrants (Young, 2017). Growing population made particular challenges for city infrastructure as well. The situation with housing in Berlin became even more acute when near a hundred thousand new arrived refugees entered the city in 2015. Besides the efforts of municipality to expand the amount of social housing for refugees, the city authorities are far to reach the amount of needed accommodation facilities. According to the State office for refugee affairs (LAF) about 28 000 migrants or 35% of all refugees remained with no access to permanent housing in 2017. The main approach of local municipality is to extend the numbers of social housing objects in the city that is usually done from the federal budget. Municipality plan is counting with an increase of 500 apartments each year to reach about 5000 new flats. All the social housing objects are built by subsidized private operators and will be provided to families with low income.

In the first phase of housing, all new-coming refugees are registered in Berlin Arrival Center where they get the first medical examination and receive a vaccination if necessary. The submission of asylum applications to the Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (BAMF) is done there as well. The German distribution system EASY determines the federal state where you need to move. This system is one of the important distribution tools and aspects of migration governance that is applied to new asylum seekers in Germany. The allocation of refugees around the whole country is based on quotas calculated in accordance with the population of each federal state and its tax revenues (Chemin, 2019). In case that Berlin is responsible for the reception of refugees, the registration in State Office for Refugee Affairs (LAF) is necessary. It is important to state that refugees have no legal right to define their allocation or move freely from one federal state to another. Even the movement through the districts of the particular federal state is limited. In this case, the right of the asylum seekers is quite constrained, at least during the residency requirement period. After the accommodation in Arriving Center refugees are moving to initial shelters. Asylum seekers are temporarily accommodated in so-called initial reception shelters where they receive few benefits during the first three to six months of their stay as asylum applicants (El-Kayed & Hamann, 2018). Initial centers are made mostly of containers and equipped with all needed facilities such as canteen. Asylum applicants receive necessary medical help and 3 meals a day. The accommodation stages in the Berlin municipality is shown in Scheme 1.

The increase of social housing has been made possible due to extending the creation of so-called “tempohomes”. Temporary houses are distributed through the Berlin districts in order to ensure that no social segregation or exclusion will be possible. Tempohomes were used in Berlin since 2016 to temporarily accommodate refugees. Tempohomes with the biggest capacity of about 1000 places are situated in the Tempelhof-Schöneberg district – one of the largest districts in terms of accommodated refugees. Berlin applied the special regulation to issue a permit for building the accommodation units that are usually located in non-residential and industrial areas such as the old Tempelhof airport where the large set of tempohomes were created (Parsloe, 2017). The city of Berlin used sports halls and schools to house asylum seekers as well. After the initial reception center refugees are moving into an apartment or get a collective accommodation with more private space and own kitchen to prepare meals. The additional costs for food are covered by higher financial benefits. Generally, there are three main types of accommodation in Berlin including emergency shelters, communal houses, and private apartments or rental housing (Soederberg, 2018).

Scheme 1 Accommodation stages for asylum seekers

Source: processed by authors

Challenge to integrate

In some federal states with lower population density and bigger territory refugees are frequently accommodated in remote areas far away from less populated settlement. However, the Berlin has a double administrative status and as a populous city there are not a lot of free locations for housing. This feature does not allow to accommodate refugees in the remote areas and become a crucial issue in the whole integration process. The infrastructure of the housing system is more developed in Berlin, however, the lack of accommodation is present and challenges the fluent migrant integration and governance. Nevertheless, the housing facilities is geographically located in the closer access to native dwellers, communities and municipality services that have a definite effect on mental, physical health and promote swifter integration process. Not only targeted accommodation facilities were used, but another social or educational premisses as well. Due to housing shortages in the city the vast range of emergency accommodation were settled, including school gyms, office buildings, exhibition or airport halls, etc. The lack of adequate housing has led to an administrative crisis in Berlin and sufficiently distorted the whole integration process.

One of the solutions to mitigate the housing crisis was the particular legal feature of the Federal state of Berlin that enables refugees to move from initial shelters and public housing units to private apartments even during the asylum application procedure. To find and get an apartment can be a quite tough due to financial support limits and long bureaucratic process related to compulsory documents and permissions. Some refugees have privileged protection and can receive immediate help from the State office for refugees matters. The groups that are covered in such a protection are, for instance, pregnant women, handicapped people, extremely ill persons, women with no family support or under-age children. However, according to El-Kayed and Hamann (2018) this housing policy was not efficient enough as sometimes refugees have faced an informational or bureaucratic barriers to move away from initial accommodation centers to private apartments. The failure of housing the refugees in Berlin are often mitigated by the local NGOs or volunteer individuals from local dwellers.

Conclusion

In 2015 about 1 million refugees and migrants mainly from Middle East and Africa have crossed the borders of Germany to organize a new life away from long-lasting conflicts. This paper assesses how refugees and asylum seekers are treated in the municipality of Berlin in terms of housing issues. According to previous studies housing has a broad impact on the

whole process of asylum seekers integration and defines the initial stages for cultural, social and economic patterns of inclusion to the environment of the receiving country. According to German authorities, housing is a key issue in the long process of integration to German society as it provides a balance in the private space of targeted group.

Regarding the housing policy and its task in asylum seekers' integration, the Berlin municipality requires a more complex and active approach. The housing constraint in the city can be considered as the most acute issue in the field of refugees' integration in the local social and cultural environment. Up to 2017, about 35% of all asylum seekers have no opportunity to move to rental housing due to the lack of permanent accommodation. The procedure to get a private apartment is still full of bureaucratic barriers and limited information, though the housing initiatives of the civil society and third sector is quite intensive.

References

- [1] Chemin, E.J. (2019). Refugee housing policy and its effects on the lives of asylum seekers in Germany. Retrived from <https://www.respondmigration.com/blog-1/refugee-housing-policy-in-germany>
- [2] D'Albis, H., Boubtane, E., & Coulibaly, D. (2018). Macroeconomic evidence suggests that asylum seekers are not a "burden" for Western European countries. *Science Advances*, 4 (6), 1-5.
- [3] El-Kayed, N., Hamann, U. (2018). Refugees' access to housing and residency in German cities: internal border regimes and their local variations. *Social inclusion*, 6(1), 135-146.
- [4] Kunzig, R. (2016). In Europe, Germany has taken in the most refugees – and struggled the most with their impact on its culture. *National geographic*, pp. 100-115.
- [5] OECD (2018). Working Together for Local Integration of Migrants and Refugees in Berlin. Retrived from <http://www.oecd.org/migration/working-together-for-local-integration-of-migrants-and-refugees-in-berlin-9789264305236-en.htm>
- [6] Parsloe, T. (2017). Berlin's Tempelhof: The Camp Too Controversial to Customize. Retrived from <https://www.newsdeeply.com/refugees/articles/2017/06/22/berlins-tempelhof-the-camp-too-controversial-to-customize>
- [7] Soederberg, S. (2018). Governing global displacement in austerity urbanism: the case of Berlin's refugee housing crisis. *Development and Change*, 50(4), 923-947.
- [8] State Office for Refugee Matters (2020). Accomodation. Retrived from <https://www.berlin.de/laf/ankommen/registrierung-laf/>
- [9] Statistisches Budesamt (2019). Asylbewerberleistungen. Retrived from <https://www.destatis.de/DE/Themen/Gesellschaft-Umwelt/Soziales/Asylbewerberleistungen/Tabellen/liste-emfaenger-bl.html>
- [10] Streitwieser, B., Brueck, L., Moody, R., & Taylor, M. (2017): The potential and reality of new refugees entering german higher education: the case of Berlin institutions. *European Education*, 49(4), 231-252.
- [11] Tomety, Y.D., Puskarova, P., Gemenne, F., & Ozer, P. (2018). The complexity of environmnetal migration: Case of the returned burkinabe fulani breeders from Bouna department in Ivory Coast to Nounbiel Province in Burkina Faso. *Medzinarodne vzťahy (Journal of International Relations)*, 16(1), 22-38. Retrived from https://fmv.euba.sk/www_write/files/dokumenty/veda-vyskum/medzinarodne-vztahy/archiv/2018/1/MV2018-1.pdf
- [12] Young, H. (2017). Finding a place to live - a near impossible endeavour for refugees. Retrived from <https://www.infomigrants.net/en/post/6268/finding-a-place-to-live-a-near-impossible-endeavour-for-refugees>
- [13] Acknowledgement:
- [14] This paper was generated within MAGYC project that has recieved funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No. 822806.